

Studies on the Mechanism of Autoxidation of Pyridinium Fluorenylides

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The course of autoxidation of 9-pyridinium and 2-nitro-9-pyridinium fluorenylides in benzene and chloroform solutions has been studied spectrophotometrically. In both the cases it obeyed the second order reaction rate law. It has been found to be a general base catalysed reaction and accordingly it has been proved to be an ionic reaction. A mechanism based on the intermediate hydro-peroxide formation has been suggested for the autoxidation of these fluorenylides.

IT has been reported earlier by Saxena and Kulshreshtha¹ that the fluorenylides decompose through an oxidative cleavage of the polar $\overset{-}{C}-\overset{+}{N}$ bond yielding fluorenone and the heterocyclic tertiary base as the products of decomposition. The decomposition of fluorenylides in solution starts immediately after they are generated, as is evidenced by the fading of their deep blue colour to a bluish green and ultimately changing to a pale yellow colour. The decomposition is very rapid, and in some cases the colour fades to a pale yellow in less than ten minutes. However, it has been observed that when these fluorenylides are extracted into oxygen free chloroform, such a fading of colour is considerably retarded. Pinck and Hilbert² made a similar observation and they showed that the ylids could be preserved for several days in a sealed tube without decomposition. The decomposition is remarkably accelerated when the ylid is extracted into chloroform through which oxygen is gradually bubbled or when the solution is exposed to sunlight. The decomposition is completely inhibited when the ylid is extracted into oxygen free chloroform and is preserved out of contact with air and sunlight. It may therefore reasonably be concluded that the decomposition is caused by oxygen and is a typical example of autoxidation which is photo sensitive. Such type of susceptibility of the ylids to the atmospheric oxygen has also been noted by various other workers, who consequently prepared ylids under conditions of rigid exclusion of air³, or in an inert atmosphere⁴ of nitrogen or argon.

The carbanion in the fluorenylides is the most obvious centre of attack for an electrophile like oxygen. The fluoryl radical has been shown to absorb one mole of oxygen per mole of fluorene, forming fluorenone as the final product in almost quantitative yields⁵. (Fluorene gives a yellow coloured fluoryl radical by the action of a base.) But in the case of fluorenylides, instances have been reported in the literature where the conjugate acid separated as the oxygen bearing moiety. Thus Johnson⁶

isolated fluorene as the product of decomposition of the stable triphenyl-arsonium fluorenylide. In a similar type of study Johnson and LaCount⁷ passed a benzene solution of tributyl-phosphonium fluorenylide over a column of alumina, which on elution yielded 44% fluorene, 48% fluorenone and the rest tri-*n*-butyl phosphine oxide. They maintain that alumina hydrolysed some of the ylid to fluorene and phosphine oxide and the rest was cleaved to fluorenone and tri-*n*-butyl phosphine which immediately got oxidised to its oxide, whereas fluorenone was most likely oxidised on alumina to fluorenone; it being found that fluorenone was gradually converted to fluorenone on an alumina column. In the present investigations however a positive colour test for the ketone was observed before the end products were subjected to chromatographic separation, and at the same time nitrogen cannot easily form an oxide with a mild oxidising agent, *viz.*, the atmospheric oxygen.

Experimental

The pyridinium fluorenylides showed a strong absorption in the visible range at 625 nm. A freshly prepared solution of the ylid obeyed the Beer's law and hence the optical density of the solution can be assumed to be proportional to the concentration of the ylid. The decomposition of the various ylids was followed with the help of Hilger spectrophotometer. All the measurements centred around 35° and were recorded at a fixed wavelength of 625 nm. The concentration of the ylid was varied, but as optical density was taken as the measure of concentration, there was not much scope for larger variations.

All the fluorenylides were prepared by the well known methods described by Saxena and Kulshreshtha¹. Spectroscopically pure chloroform and benzene were used for the extraction of the fluorenylide. As soon as the ylid was generated from an aqueous solution of the quaternary pyridinium fluorenyl bromide, it was extracted into a known volume

of chloroform or benzene. As the concentration of the ylid generated for this purpose was very low, normally one extraction was found to be sufficient to extract the whole amount of the ylid generated from the known weight of the quaternary salt. The measurements of optical density were made immediately after transferring the ylid solution into the glass cell, but no readings could be recorded for the zero time, as entire operation of extraction and transfer of the ylid solution to the glass cell took nearly one minute on an average.

The reciprocal of optical density was plotted against time, t , measured in minutes. A straight line was obtained in each case till about 60% of the reaction is over, which is a range more than sufficient to study the reaction kinetics. The rate of formation of fluorenone, a yellow coloured compound absorbing below 400 nm, could not be studied as its absorption is masked by that of the ylid. The results obtained are given below in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

TABLE 1. DECOMPOSITION OF 9-PYRIDINIUM FLUORENYLIDE FOLLOWED THROUGH SPECTROPHOTOMETER

Temperature 35°		Wavelength 625 nm			
Solvent	Concentration of the fluorenylide in gm. moles $\times 10^{-4}$ /litre	Time 't' in minutes	Optical density 'O.D.'	1/O.D.	K_2 velocity coefficient
Chloroform	1.32	1.5	0.405	2.469	
		3	0.330	3.030	
		4	0.280	3.571	
		5	0.265	3.774	
		6	0.245	4.082	
		7	0.232	4.310	
		9	0.192	5.076	
		10	0.190	5.263	
		12	0.174	5.747	
		14	0.166	6.024	0.31

TABLE 2. K_2 FOR 9-PYRIDINIUM FLUORENYLIDE

Temperature 35°		Wavelength 625 nm	
Solvent	Concentration of ylid in g. mole $\times 10^{-4}$ /litre	Velocity coefficient	
Chloroform	1.32	0.31	
	2.62	0.28	
	3.96	0.17	
Benzene	1.32	0.18	
	2.64	0.14	
	3.96	0.08	

Figures 1 and 2 show the linear relationship between $1/O.D.$ and time t . This linear relationship between t and $1/(a-x)$ indicates that the autoxidation of fluorenylides obeys a second order reaction rate law. However, the usual relationship between the velocity constant and the concentration of the ylid was not observed; on the contrary a decrease in the rate

TABLE 3. K_2 FOR 2-NITRO 9-PYRIDINIUM FLUORENYLIDE

Temperature 35°		Wavelength 625 nm	
Solvent	Concentration of ylid in g. mole $\times 10^{-4}$ /litre	Velocity coefficient	
Chloroform	1.04	0.034	
	2.08	0.023	
	3.12	0.019	
Benzene	1.041	0.021	
	2.082	0.017	
	3.123	0.014	

constant with an increase of the concentration of the ylid was observed.

Fig. 1. Decomposition of 9-Pyridinium fluorenylide in chloroform and benzene

○—○ $\sim 1.32 \times 10^{-4}$ g. moles/litre
 ●—● $\sim 2.64 \times 10^{-4}$ g. moles/litre
 ○—○ $\sim 3.96 \times 10^{-4}$ g. moles/litre
 - - - in chloroform
 ——— in benzene.

The second order reaction rate law involved in this reaction of these fluorenylides was further confirmed by plotting dy/dx against $\log C$, which gave a straight line, but the anomalous decrease in the value of the rate constant remained inexplicable.

It was observed that when a hydroxylic substance *e.g.*, ethanol, phenol or hydroquinone was added to a solution of the fluorenylide, an instantaneous disappearance of the blue colour of the ylid took place. The autoxidation of the ylid was also found to be catalysed by a base *e.g.*, pyridine or piperidine. The effect of pyridine on the autoxidation of 9-pyridinium fluorenylide is shown in Table 4, which shows an increase in the values of the velocity

Fig. 2. Decomposition 2-Nitro 9-Pyridinium fluorenylide in chloroform and benzene

- ~ 1.04 × 10⁻⁴ g. moles/litre
- 2.08 × 10⁻⁴ g. moles/litre
- 3.12 × 10⁻⁴ g. moles/litre
- in chloroform
- in benzene.

constant with an increase in the concentration of pyridine in the solution.

TABLE 4

(Pyridine) × 10 ⁻⁵ g. moles/litre	(Fluorenylide), × 10 ⁻⁴ g. moles/litre	Second order rate constant K ₂
—	3.96	0.17
2.55	"	0.33
5.06	"	0.40
7.59	"	0.47
10.10	"	0.53

This should explain the decrease in the values of the rate constant with the increase in the concentration of the ylid. Because for lower concentrations of the ylid a small amount of pyridine (obtained as the product of decomposition of the fluorenylide) should be able to catalyse the reaction to a larger extent. (see Tables 2 and 3).

Discussion

It may be seen from Table 4 and other experiments already described that the process of autoxidation of fluorenylides is a general base catalysed reaction. It may be seen that even a free radical reaction inhibitor accelerates the decomposition of the ylid. Moreover the reaction is faster in chloroform than in benzene, thereby indicating that the heterolytic cleavage of the ylid is favoured by a polar solvent. Based on these facts it is inferred that autoxidation of fluorenylides should be an ionic reaction.

The above cleavage seems to be preceded by the hydroperoxide formation. It is a natural corollary to the work of Sprinzac who has reported the formation of a coloured fluoryl radical by the action of Triton-B on fluorene in a solution of pyridine. The fluoryl radical is oxidised to fluorenone through an intermediate hydroperoxide⁵ which was isolated by Sprinzac. This is explained in Scheme 1.

Based on above facts that the carbanion of the fluoryl radical is the centre of attack by the electrophil, oxygen, which ultimately results in the formation of fluorenone through an intermediate hydroperoxide formation; the following mechanism can also be cited for the autoxidation of the fluorenylides. The reaction has been suggested to take place in an identical manner as Scheme 1 in two steps. In the first step the hydroperoxide formation of the ylid takes place, and in the second step the hydroperoxide formed from the ylid further reacts with another molecule of the ylid to give fluorenone as the end product. It will be shown in the discussion further that two molecules of ylid are involved in this reaction which are ultimately affected in the disappearance of colour, the overall reaction should be a second order reaction. (see Scheme II).

STEP-1

(1) Experimentally, the rate at which A (the fluorenylide) is disappearing in two steps is being determined. As the concentration of dissolved oxygen is constant, the rate at which 'A' would react with oxygen will, be proportional to the concentration of 'A'. Further the presence of the base is needed (even water can act as a base) to bring about the change of 'A' to 'B'. This would explain the base catalysis of the reaction. Thus the rate at which A changes to B depends upon the concentrations of both A and the base, (see Table 4).

(2) A and B react with C and ultimately D is formed. Thus the rate of the overall reaction will be proportional to the product of concentrations of A and B at a given concentration of the base which act as a catalyst. But since the rate at which B is produced depends upon the concentration of A, the rate at which A and B would react, would be proportional to $[A]^2$. This is in keeping with the second order reaction rate law which is observed in this case.

(3) Since oxygen is required in the initial first step of this reaction, it should imply that no decomposition of fluorenylide would take place in the absence

of oxygen, a phenomenon which has been verified experimentally.

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